

1 Markers in the blood in humans with hepatitis B.

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7 We measured total transcription in CD4 lymphocytes isolated from the blood of humans with acute liver
8 failure resulting from hepatitis B infection. We also measured total transcription in the human liver during
9 authentic HBV infection. Interestingly, genes induced in the liver in humans with HBV infection *in vivo*,
10 genes corresponding to immunologic systems including XCL1 and CXCL10, were contrarily silenced in
11 T-cells in the periphery. To support deconvolution of cell and tissue dependent transcriptome signature in
12 humans with HBV we measured total transcription by RNA-sequencing in CD161+ CD8+ circulating
13 non-MAIT T-cells from healthy donors and from HBV+ individuals. CD161+ CD8+ circulating non-MAIT
14 T-cells expressed high quantities of the tetratricopeptide cell surface marker TTC16 and the solute carrier
15 SLC38A10. Interleukin-16 production was a transcriptional hallmark of the HBV+ gene signature in this
16 T-cell type, as was silencing of IL21R and IL4R. Other elements of immunologic activation in HBV+
17 CD161+ CD8+ circulating non-MAIT T-cells was activation of Irf3, Gimap6, PTPN6 and CARD8. HBV+
18 CD161+ CD8+ circulating non-MAIT T-cells expressed Trim14 and Samd19 and silenced ABCF1 and
19 Zdhc7. IL16 activation concomitant with induction of TTC16 in CD161+ CD8+ circulating non-MAIT
20 T-cells marks HBV infection in the blood in humans.

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